

Excess viscosities (η^E) of glycine with halide salts of alkali metals of IA group in aqueous solutions at 310.15 K for structural interactions^ψ

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Density $\rho \pm 1 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and viscosity $\eta \pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for 0.01 to 0.33 mol kg⁻¹ lithium to cesium chloride and iodide salts, and glycine (Gly) 0.01 to 0.10 mol kg⁻¹ in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ salts have been measured at pH = 7. The data were regressed and extrapolated to zero concentrations ($m = 0$) for limiting density (ρ^0), viscosity (η^0) and slopes (S_d) and S_η values, respectively. Relative viscosities (η_r) are fitted to extended Jones-Dole equation for intrinsic viscosity (B at $m = 0$) and slope (D) values, the ρ^0 and η^0 are intensive while and S_d and D extensive functions. Thus the formers illustrate ion-water, ion-Gly and ion-water-Gly while latter the ion-ion interactions, and the B size of hydrated ion and ion-Gly associations. The ρ^0 and B values increase with composition except RbCl and B of Gly are higher for RbCl and CsI, and ρ^0 for RbCl and NaI. Their values are rationalized with shell size, filled and unfilled d orbital. Excess viscosities (η^E) were calculated from η and fitted to Redlich-Kister equation for excess viscosity function (Y^E). It explains deviations from ideal behavior on ion-ion-water, Gly-ion-ion, Gly-ion-water, Gly-Gly-ion and Gly-Gly-water interactions.

Physico-chemical characterization of amino acids in aqueous halide salts of Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ has not been reported, although Gly density for aqueous NaCl and KCl have been obtained but the viscosity are to be measured yet. Thus the halide salts have been chosen and are of bio-physical, physiological¹ and industrial interests^{2,3}. Long ago Traube⁴ had derived partial molal volumes^{5,6} of biomolecule from density and of sodium and potassium chloride systems⁷⁻¹², need updating. More so Landolt-Bornstein³ and Lobo⁵ had reviewed structural interactions of aqueous solutions of limited salts¹³⁻²¹ from 1976 to 1988. Notably ⁺NH₃-CH₂-COO⁻ of Gly due to N⁺ and O⁻ ionic atoms induce intra/intermolecular interactions causing torsional forces and disruption of electron distribution forming dipoles, which can deform, stress or strain solutions depicted by ρ and η data thus salt-amino acid interactions are of fundamental significance for biochemical sciences^{22,23}. Their excess viscosities²⁴ examine the type and strength of interactions between the salts and Gly.

Results and discussion

The ρ values are calculated from equation,

$$\rho = ((w - w_e)/w_0 - w_e)\rho_0 + 0.0012(1 - ((w - w_e)/w_0 - w_e)) \quad (1)$$

The w_e , w , and w_0 are weights of empty, solution and solvent filled pycnometer, respectively. The ρ , ρ_0 and 0.0012 are solution, solvent and air density, respectively, $(1 - ((w - w_e)/w_0 - w_e))$ buoyancy correction. The η and η_r are calculated from relations.

$$\eta = (\rho \cdot t)/(\rho_0 \cdot t_0)\eta_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_r = (\rho \cdot t)/(\rho_0 \cdot t_0) \quad (3)$$

The t and t_0 flow times for solution and solvent, errors in ρ and η data are calculated with statistical methods given elsewhere²⁵. The η_r was fitted to Jones-Dole equation.

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta^0 = 1 + Am^{1/2} + Bm \quad (4)$$

where A is Falkenhagen²⁶ constant, B intrinsic viscosity/Jones-Dole coefficient, the A is found negligible for Gly systems and omitted. Thus extended Jones-Dole^{25,27} equation is used.

$$(\eta_r - 1)/m = B + Dm \quad (5)$$

The D is slope, excess viscosity (η^E) was calculated from eqn.

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

$$\eta^E = \eta - \exp(x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2) \quad (6) \quad Y^E = x_1 x_2 \sum \eta^E (1 - 2x_1)^{j-1} \quad (7)$$

The x_1 and x_2 mole fractions of solute and solvent and η_1 and η_2 viscosities, respectively, for calculation of excess viscosity function (Y^E) by Redlich-Kister relation²⁸ given below.

The ρ^0 values are fitted to $\rho = \rho^0 + S_d \cdot m$ relation, primary data given in Table 1, the ρ^0 values for aq. NaCl and KCl compared with literature in Table 2 show a close agreement.

Table 1. Density and viscosity, reduced and excess viscosity of aqueous salt systems

$m, \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$	$\rho, 10^3 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \pm 10^{-5}$	$\eta, 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \pm 10^{-5}$	$\eta_{\text{red}}, 10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$	$\eta^E, 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Salt systems				
Chlorides, LiCl				
0	0.99338 ± 5.2430	0.69470 ± 19.91		
0.0114	0.99448 ± 5.2600	0.71788 ± 20.90		
0.0699	0.99565 ± 5.2600	0.70258 ± 21.17	2.94015	0.02282
0.1100	0.99634 ± 5.2500	0.70356 ± 21.16	0.16242	0.00724
0.1500	0.99712 ± 5.2400	0.67723 ± 21.15	0.11596	0.00780
0.2050	0.99816 ± 5.2300	0.64921 ± 21.13	-0.16764	-0.01490
0.2900	0.99977 ± 5.2250	0.57919 ± 20.45	-0.31939	-0.03598
0.3344	1.00062 ± 5.2200	0.55736 ± 20.04	-0.57335	-0.07987
			-0.59119	-0.08805
NaCl				
0.0050	0.99424 ± 5.2600	0.69882 ± 21.21	1.19351	0.00400
0.0101	0.99441 ± 5.2600	0.70004 ± 21.19	0.76435	0.00518
0.0506	0.99711 ± 5.2500	0.70395 ± 21.16	0.26300	0.00869
0.0988	0.99796 ± 5.2500	0.70834 ± 21.10	0.19888	0.01221
0.5115	1.01351 ± 5.1700	0.73509 ± 20.85	0.11366	0.01998
1.0398	1.03341 ± 5.0900	0.77560 ± 20.47	0.11199	-0.00337
KCl				
0.0105	0.99405 ± 5.2600	0.69441 ± 21.28	-0.04011	-0.00039
0.0521	0.99607 ± 5.2500	0.69855 ± 21.24	0.10635	0.00355
0.1073	0.99867 ± 5.2400	0.70251 ± 21.20	0.10473	0.00689
0.1500	1.00072 ± 5.2300	0.70624 ± 21.04	0.11077	0.00974
0.2050	1.00334 ± 5.2200	0.71081 ± 19.56	0.11311	0.01276
0.2900	1.00739 ± 5.2100	0.71786 ± 19.14	0.11498	0.01646
0.3344	1.00951 ± 5.2000	0.72155 ± 19.98	0.11558	0.01793
RbCl				
0.0102	0.99445 ± 5.2600	0.69473 ± 21.28	0.00401	-0.00007
0.0468	0.99562 ± 5.2600	0.69430 ± 21.31	-0.01243	-0.00048
0.1839	0.99999 ± 5.2500	0.69372 ± 21.32	-0.00771	-0.00088
0.1500	0.99891 ± 5.2400	0.69370 ± 21.13	-0.00956	-0.00093
0.2050	1.00067 ± 5.2300	0.69377 ± 20.13	-0.00653	-0.00081
0.2900	1.00339 ± 5.2200	0.69439 ± 20.02	-0.00154	-0.00028
0.3344	1.00480 ± 5.2100	0.69497 ± 19.92	0.00114	0.00013
CsCl				
0.0101	0.99524 ± 5.2600	0.69964 ± 21.21	0.70655	0.00479
0.0504	1.00060 ± 5.2300	0.70020 ± 21.26	0.15720	0.00513
0.1014	1.00728 ± 5.2000	0.70607 ± 21.24	0.16134	0.01014
0.1500	1.01369 ± 5.1200	0.70892 ± 21.13	0.13644	0.01202
0.2050	1.02093 ± 5.1100	0.71290 ± 20.72	0.12777	0.01443

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Table-1 (contd.)

0.2900	1.03213 ± 4.9500	0.71904 ± 20.37	0.12083	0.01730
0.3344	1.03798 ± 4.9100	0.72225 ± 20.12	0.11861	0.01840
Iodides, LiI				
0.0114	0.99585 ± 5.2600	0.69720 ± 20.90	0.31515	0.00236
0.0699	1.00095 ± 5.2600	0.69984 ± 21.17	0.10591	0.00469
0.1100	1.00445 ± 5.2500	0.70166 ± 21.16	0.09105	0.00611
0.1500	1.00793 ± 5.2400	0.70347 ± 21.14	0.08414	0.00738
0.2050	1.01272 ± 5.2300	0.70596 ± 21.01	0.07904	0.00889
0.2900	1.02012 ± 5.2200	0.70980 ± 20.24	0.07496	0.01069
0.3344	1.02399 ± 5.2100	0.71181 ± 20.05	0.07366	0.01138
NaI				
0.0103	0.99589 ± 5.2600	0.70032 ± 21.21	0.78490	0.00546
0.0516	1.00020 ± 5.2400	0.69779 ± 21.30	0.08620	0.00283
0.1020	1.00549 ± 5.2100	0.69926 ± 21.34	0.06441	0.00401
0.1500	1.01052 ± 5.2000	0.70533 ± 21.09	0.10199	0.00896
0.2050	1.01628 ± 5.1900	0.71786 ± 20.76	0.16262	0.01840
0.2900	1.02519 ± 5.1800	0.74896 ± 20.14	0.26932	0.03888
0.3344	1.02984 ± 5.1780	0.77087 ± 19.98	0.32787	0.05151
KI				
0.0509	0.99998 ± 5.2400	0.69418 ± 21.36	-0.01481	-0.00059
0.1013	1.00573 ± 5.2100	0.69759 ± 21.37	0.04110	0.00251
0.1016	1.00576 ± 5.2000	0.70473 ± 21.25	0.14218	0.00893
0.1500	1.01128 ± 5.1900	0.70791 ± 21.05	0.12673	0.01116
0.2050	1.01755 ± 5.1800	0.71553 ± 20.76	0.14629	0.01653
0.2900	1.02725 ± 5.1700	0.72732 ± 20.24	0.16194	0.02325
0.3344	1.03231 ± 5.1600	0.73348 ± 20.11	0.16694	0.02599
RbI				
0.0101	0.99298 ± 5.2700	0.68108 ± 21.51	-1.94744	-0.01358
0.0504	0.99959 ± 5.2400	0.68998 ± 21.43	-0.13463	-0.00458
0.1010	1.00744 ± 5.2000	0.70246 ± 21.31	0.11065	0.00689
0.1500	1.01529 ± 5.1200	0.71385 ± 21.11	0.18377	0.01623
0.2050	1.02403 ± 4.9900	0.72682 ± 20.91	0.22552	0.02558
0.2900	1.03754 ± 4.9200	0.74686 ± 20.22	0.25889	0.03736
0.3344	1.04460 ± 4.8000	0.75732 ± 20.10	0.26957	0.04222
CsI				
0.0101	0.99588 ± 5.2600	0.69576 ± 21.28	0.15157	0.00095
0.0507	1.00371 ± 5.2200	0.69707 ± 21.35	0.06723	0.00215
0.1017	1.01359 ± 5.1800	0.69336 ± 21.54	-0.01898	-0.00129
0.1500	1.02292 ± 5.1300	0.68436 ± 21.23	-0.09920	-0.00886
0.2050	1.03355 ± 5.0100	0.66762 ± 21.09	-0.19017	-0.02151
0.2900	1.04998 ± 4.9100	0.62812 ± 20.64	-0.33046	-0.04663
0.3344	1.05857 ± 4.8100	0.60092 ± 20.12	-0.40368	-0.06094
Gly for 0.01 m LiCl				
0	0.99447 ± 5.2150	0.73882 ± 21.02		
0.0101	0.99512 ± 5.2600	0.67634 ± 21.22	-2.62642	0.00162
0.0313	0.99575 ± 5.2600	0.67780 ± 21.20	-0.77790	0.00301

Table-1 (contd.)

0.0501	0.99671 ± 5.2600	0.67765 ± 21.22	-0.49011	0.00281
0.0699	0.99715 ± 5.2500	0.68140 ± 21.16	-0.27389	0.00624
0.0993	0.99945 ± 5.2400	0.68849 ± 21.06	-0.08994	0.01244
		0.01 <i>m</i> NaCl		
0	0.99469 ± 5.2500	0.70029 ± 21.04		
0.0950	0.99417 ± 5.2600	0.69389 ± 21.21	-0.23262	0.00091
0.0101	0.99432 ± 5.2600	0.69038 ± 21.27	-0.61803	-0.00257
0.0152	0.99448 ± 5.2500	0.69328 ± 21.21	-0.13499	0.00030
0.0202	0.99463 ± 5.24600	0.69580 ± 21.18	0.07814	0.00277
0.0266	0.99482 ± 5.24300	0.69506 ± 21.20	0.01940	0.00203
0.0503	0.99554 ± 5.24200	0.69514 ± 21.20	0.01272	0.00206
		0.01 <i>m</i> KCl		
0	0.99404 ± 5.2400	0.69462 ± 21.08		
0.0101	0.99363 ± 5.2600	0.69770 ± 21.23	0.42723	0.00011
0.0304	0.99423 ± 5.2600	0.70062 ± 21.19	0.28072	0.00294
0.0507	0.99473 ± 5.2600	0.70041 ± 21.20	0.16219	0.00268
0.0711	0.99540 ± 5.2500	0.70395 ± 21.14	0.18725	0.00591
0.1009	0.99623 ± 5.2500	0.70734 ± 21.10	0.18034	0.00878
		0.01 <i>m</i> RbCl		
0	0.99444 ± 5.2500	0.69472 ± 21.11		
0.0100	0.99617 ± 5.2600	0.70691 ± 21.45	1.75802	0.00004
0.0299	0.99690 ± 5.2600	0.70973 ± 21.06	0.72384	0.00278
0.0502	0.99747 ± 5.2500	0.71142 ± 21.04	0.47928	0.00433
0.0705	0.99804 ± 5.2500	0.71650 ± 20.97	0.44514	0.00896
0.1011	0.99957 ± 5.2400	0.71882 ± 20.95	0.34350	0.01076
		0.01 <i>m</i> CsCl		
0	0.99525 ± 5.2550	0.69879 ± 21.01		
0.0101	0.99723 ± 5.2600	0.69869 ± 21.17	0.56979	-0.00042
0.0302	0.99796 ± 5.2500	0.70214 ± 21.12	0.35427	0.00293
0.0504	0.99872 ± 5.2500	0.70324 ± 21.11	0.24405	0.00392
0.0714	0.99923 ± 5.2500	0.70538 ± 21.08	0.21525	0.00582
0.1002	0.99958 ± 5.2400	0.70872 ± 21.03	0.20150	0.00865
		0.01 <i>m</i> LiI		
0	0.99447 ± 5.2340	0.69713 ± 19.65		
0.0101	0.9971766 ± 5.2600	0.69168 ± 21.22	-0.43046	0.00005
0.0313	0.9981351 ± 5.2600	0.69351 ± 21.20	-0.05495	0.00182
0.0501	0.998985 ± 5.2600	0.69512 ± 21.22	0.01219	0.00333
0.0699	0.9998802 ± 5.2500	0.69683 ± 21.16	0.04384	0.00484
0.0993	1.0012094 ± 5.2400	0.69936 ± 21.06	0.06756	0.00698
		0.01 <i>m</i> NaI		
0	0.99585 ± 5.2200	0.70035 ± 19.45		
0.0100	0.99637 ± 5.2600	0.69233 ± 21.25	-0.34153	-0.00043
0.0300	0.99697 ± 5.2600	0.69640 ± 21.19	0.08135	0.00353
0.0501	0.99782 ± 5.2500	0.69450 ± 21.23	-0.00561	0.00165
0.0701	0.99889 ± 5.2500	0.69902 ± 21.17	0.08872	0.00582
0.0992	0.99976 ± 5.2400	0.70106 ± 21.14	0.09231	0.00748

		0.01 m KI		
0	0.99531 ± 5.2100	0.69849 ± 19.34		
0.0101	0.99558 ± 5.2600	0.69327 ± 21.28	-0.20371	-0.00063
0.0303	0.99606 ± 5.2600	0.69686 ± 21.22	0.10235	0.00287
0.0502	0.99660 ± 5.2500	0.69746 ± 21.22	0.07917	0.00338
0.0708	0.99751 ± 5.2500	0.70049 ± 21.18	0.11761	0.00613
0.1011	0.99862 ± 5.2400	0.70244 ± 21.16	0.11017	0.00768
		0.01 m RbI		
0	0.99304 ± 5.2651	0.68084 ± 21.22		
0.0301	0.99323 ± 5.2700	0.70860 ± 21.27	0.66442	0.00216
0.0504	0.99437 ± 5.2600	0.71084 ± 21.25	0.46108	0.00425
0.0704	0.99493 ± 5.2600	0.71468 ± 21.19	0.40880	0.00773
0.1004	0.99596 ± 5.2500	0.71681 ± 21.29	0.31709	0.00940
0.1006	0.99571 ± 5.2500	0.71698 ± 21.16	0.31882	0.00955
		0.01 m CsI		
0	0.99586 ± 5.2500	0.69372 ± 21.03		
0.0100	0.99352 ± 5.2600	0.69185 ± 21.30	-0.40988	0.00054
0.0299	0.99408 ± 5.2600	0.69349 ± 21.28	-0.05836	0.00212
0.0503	0.99450 ± 5.2500	0.69567 ± 21.25	0.02762	0.00415
0.0704	0.99527 ± 5.2500	0.69696 ± 21.24	0.04622	0.00526
0.1002	0.99638 ± 5.2500	0.70217 ± 21.16	0.10734	0.00979

Table 2. Comparison of density of NaCl and KCl aqueous systems calculated from regression constants of primary data given in Table 3 and literature values at 310.15 K

<i>m</i> , mol kg ⁻¹	ρ , 10 ³ kg m ⁻³ , NaCl			ρ , 10 ³ kg m ⁻³ , KCl		
	Exp.	Lit.	Exp. - Lit.	Exp.	Lit.	Exp. - Lit.
0.1	0.99807	0.99735	0.00072	0.99833	0.99796	0.00037
0.5	1.01310	1.01296	0.00013	1.01741	1.01578	0.00163
1.0	1.03188	1.03177	0.00011	1.04126	1.03711	0.00415

Literature : Alexander Apelblat and Emanuel Manzurola, *J. Thermodynamics*, 1999, 31, 869.

The values of the ρ^0 and η^0 along with η^E are given in Table 3 and constants of Jones-Dole equation along with Y^E in Table 4. The differences in the values of ρ^0 and η^0 of chloride and iodide salts are given in Table 5, the plots of η^E vs x_2 and Y^E vs x_2 are drawn in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The Y^E values for corresponding salts and with Gly are plotted in Fig. 3. Experimental ρ^0 values for NaCl²² and Gly^{28,29} are in agreement with literature, the densities of aq. CsCl and CsI increase with composition with maximum values among salt systems.

The ρ^0 values for aq. chloride salts are found in order of NaCl > LiCl > RbCl > CsCl > KCl and for iodides as LiI > NaI > KI > CsI > RbI. Li⁺ and Na⁺ owing to their small size and higher charge density form a long

range arrangement, ordered, large sized hydration sphere, void volume is occupied by free water molecules resulting in its high value. The KCl has exceptionally low value and attributed to its polarizability. With I⁻, the trend is seen in accordance with charge density except Rb⁺ may be because of comparable sizes between Cs⁺ and Rb⁺. Thus, charge density fails to monitor the size of hydration sphere.

However the ρ^0 values of iodides are found higher than those of chlorides except RbCl > RbI and CsCl > CsI which signifies that I⁻ enhances packing strength more than Cl⁻ but with large sized cations. Likewise, the *B* values (Table 4) for salts are listed as LiCl > NaCl > CsCl > RbCl > KCl and NaI > LiI > CsI > KI >

Table 3. The regression constants of density and viscosity of binary and ternary systems

Systems	$\rho^0 \pm 10^{-5}$, 10^3 kg m^{-3}	$S_d \pm 10^{-5}$, $10^3 \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$\eta \pm 10^{-5}$, $10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$S_\eta \pm 10^{-5}$, $10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$S_\eta \pm 10^{-5}$, $(10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1})^2$
Aqueous salts					
LiCl	0.99428 ± 10.00	0.01894 ± 5.0	0.74413 ± 33.0	-0.53123 ± 17.0	
NaCl	0.99430 ± 10.00	0.03756 ± 4.0	0.69956 ± 28.0	0.07256 ± 10.0	
KCl	0.99356 ± 9.50	0.04770 ± 4.3	0.69379 ± 28.0	0.08302 ± 10.0	
RbCl	0.99412 ± 48.00	0.31950 ± 39.0	0.69487 ± 48.0	-0.01435 ± 39.0	-0.04378 ± 13.0
CsCl	0.99393 ± 14.00	0.13172 ± 8.0	0.69807 ± 20.0	0.07232 ± 2.0	
LiI	0.99763 ± 6.00	0.04624 ± 1.0	0.69668 ± 6.0	0.04525 ± 1.0	
NaI	0.99480 ± 9.00	0.10478 ± 4.0	0.70147 ± 9.0	-0.12221 ± 4.0	0.98608 ± 12.0
KI	0.99417 ± 10.00	0.11406 ± 5.0	0.68710 ± 10.0	0.13869 ± 5.0	
RbI	0.99145 ± 14.00	0.15894 ± 9.0	0.67848 ± 28.0	0.23577 ± 9.0	
CsI	0.99392 ± 12.00	0.19331 ± 7.0	0.69485 ± 61.0	0.10169 ± 56	-1.14412 ± 9.0
Gly for aqueous salts					
LiCl	0.99438 ± 30.00	0.04720 ± 13.0	0.67342 ± 30.0	0.13271 ± 13.0	
NaCl	0.99402 ± 31.90	0.03010 ± 15.5	0.6912 ± 31.9	0.20757 ± 15.5	-2.51617 ± 14.0
KCl	0.99333 ± 10.00	0.02870 ± 5.0	0.69661 ± 28.0	0.10254 ± 10.0	
RbCl	0.99575 ± 11.00	0.03602 ± 6.0	0.70555 ± 48.0	0.13617 ± 39.0	
CsCl	0.99715 ± 9.00	0.02649 ± 4.0	0.69811 ± 31.0	0.10531 ± 14.0	
LiI	0.99672 ± 10.00	0.04521 ± 5.0	0.69081 ± 35.0	0.08611 ± 20.0	
NaI	0.99590 ± 11.00	0.03968 ± 6.0	0.69189 ± 30.0	0.09197 ± 13.0	
KI	0.99508 ± 12.00	0.03412 ± 7.0	0.69297 ± 29.0	0.09783 ± 17.0	
RbI	0.99238 ± 28.00	-0.03501 ± 9.0	0.70523 ± 28.0	0.11863 ± 9.0	
CsI	0.99311 ± 12.00	0.03153 ± 7.0	0.69024 ± 31.0	0.11092 ± 14.0	

Table 4. The coefficient, B ($10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$), slope, D ($10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$)² of regression of $(\eta_r - 1)/m$ vs m fitted to Jones-Dole equation and excess viscosity function Y^E

Systems	$B \pm 10^{-4}$ $10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$	$D \pm 10^{-6}$ $(10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1})^2$	$D' \pm 10^{-5}$ $(10^{-3} \text{ kg mol}^{-1})^3$	Y^E $10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Chloride salt systems				
LiCl	2.7588 ± 2	-29.4444 ± 90	60.2567 ± 30	0.11740
NaCl	0.7309 ± 2	-2.4444 ± 0.2	1.8108 ± 0.1	-0.02449
KCl	-0.0117 ± 2	1.3112 ± 4	-2.9101 ± 0.3	-0.04319
RbCl	-0.0003 ± 2	-0.1147 ± 0.2	0.3699 ± 0.2	0.00218
CsCl	0.5921 ± 2	-4.9158 ± 80	10.9521 ± 2	-0.05292
Iodide salt systems				
LiI	0.3001 ± 2	-2.2605 ± 0.1	4.9357 ± 2	-0.03342
NaI	0.6385 ± 2	-6.4992 ± 2	17.3904 ± 2	-0.08377
KI	-0.0829 ± 2	1.9712 ± 8	-3.7616 ± 0.4	-0.05776
RbI	-1.6192 ± 2	19.9573 ± 2	-41.8656 ± 50	-0.07087
CsI	0.1579 ± 2	-1.6895 ± 2		0.08765
Gly for salt systems				
LiCl	-3.2142 ± 2	81.4868 ± 20	513.9732 ± 50	0.02588
NaCl	-0.5933 ± 2	35.7506 ± 1	-467.1321 ± 30	0.00376
KCl	0.5101 ± 2	-9.4113 ± 2	61.7941 ± 90	0.02038
RbCl	2.0776 ± 2	-46.7671 ± 0.2	299.4460 ± 23	0.02670
CsCl	0.6719 ± 2	-12.0951 ± 80	74.7880 ± 37	0.02080

Table-4 (contd.)

LiI	-0.5560 ± 2	17.0652 ± 0.1	-110.7306 ± 2	0.01688
NaI	-0.4127 ± 2	14.4045 ± 6	-96.2392 ± 2	0.01783
KI	-0.2704 ± 2	11.6061 ± 6	-79.3147 ± 4	0.01936
RbI	0.9955 ± 2	-13.3241 ± 6	65.7835 ± 70	0.03996
CsI	-0.5167 ± 2	15.6370 ± 7	-96.2326 ± 1	0.02168

Table 5. The $\Delta\rho^0 = \rho^0$ (iodide-chloride) and $\Delta\eta = \eta$ (iodide-chloride) systems in aqueous

Systems	Aqueous salts		Gly in salts	
	$\Delta\rho$	$\Delta\eta$	$\Delta\rho$	$\Delta\eta$
LiI-LiCl	0.00336	-0.04745	0.00234	0.01739
NaI-NaCl	0.00050	0.00191	0.00188	0.00069
KI-KCl	0.00061	-0.00669	0.00175	-0.00364
RbI-RbCl	-0.00027	-0.01639	-0.00337	-0.00032
CsI-CsCl	-0.00001	-0.00322	-0.00404	-0.00787

RbI, and depict size of hydrated molecules/ions. The B values are positive for Li^+ , Na^+ and Cs^+ and negative for K^+ and Rb^+ , it strengthens the molecular forces and infers that Li^+ , Na^+ and Cs^+ act as water breaker while K^+ and Rb^+ as makers. The Li^+ with effective nuclear charge causes greater influence on water structure forming hydration spheres with similar behavior for Na^+ . The Cs^+ acts as water structure breaker due to size effect that dominates over effective nuclear charge (Table 4), the B values for chloride are higher than of iodide salts

Fig. 1. Viscosity of salt and Gly systems at 310.15 K, the m of salts and Gly is plotted on X-axis.

Fig. 2. Y-axis =Excess viscosity of Gly in aqueous chloride and iodide salts systems at 37°C, X-axis mole fraction of system.

except CsCl with ± 2.2 to 0.07 difference in values.

Slope constant S_d :

It rationalizes to an influence of salt composition on ion-ion, pairwise interactions with values as $RbCl > CsCl > KCl > NaCl > LiCl$ and $CsI > RbI > KI > NaI > LiI$. This depicts a decrease in S_d values with size of cations except Rb^+ , with no influence of size of anion on ion-ion interactions. However S_d values from CsI to LiI decrease with higher values for iodide salts than of chlorides, also RbCl has higher S_d than of CsCl perhaps stronger screening on Rb^+ causes stronger Rb^+-Rb^+ pairwise interactions. It makes higher composition impact on them but filled 4d weaken screening effect and Cs^+-Cs^+ interactions however from KCl to LiCl the S_d are noted to decrease by about ± 0.05 .

Ternary systems :

The ρ^0 order of Gly-salt system are found in order of

$CsCl > RbCl > LiCl > KCl > NaCl$ and $LiI > NaI > KI > CsI > RbI$ with higher value for iodides than of chlorides except RbCl and attributed to an effective hydration of Cl^- as compared to I^- due to size. The trend of ρ^0 of iodide salts is same in binary and ternary systems and attributes to the fact that ion-hydration complex of iodide salts seem to be compact. It may not facilitate the interactions with Gly pushing it towards outer surface of complex. Hence Gly is not able to break ion-hydration structure and get associated around hydration spheres due to electrostatic interactions with formation of larger hydrosphere. Thus the ρ^0 values seems to be constituted of four factors as $(\rho_{vw} + \rho_v) + (\rho_s + \rho_h)$, the ρ_{vw} represents intrinsic interactions ($m = 0$) or van der Waal attraction force, ρ_v void volume, ρ_s contribution of solute-solvent interactions and ρ_h , the hydrophobic hydration. The $(\rho_{vw} + \rho_s)$ is approximately same in water and aq-

Fig. 3. Y-axis – salt and Gly systems and X-axis – excess function (Y^E), the Y^E values are shown along the bars.

salts so change in $(\rho_s + \rho_h)$ must explain a trend of ρ^0 and ρ_{tr}^0 (density transfer from binary to ternary systems). Thus $(\rho_s + \rho_h)$ of Gly for salt is taken as.

$$(\rho_s + \rho_v)_{aq\ salt} = \rho_{sg} + \rho_{ss} + \rho_{sw} + \rho_{ww} \quad (8)$$

The ρ_{sg} , ρ_{ss} , ρ_{sw} and ρ_{ww} are contributions from salt-Gly, salt-salt, salt-water and dipole-dipole interactions respectively, ρ_{tr}^0 calculated as.

$$\rho_{tr}^0 = (\rho_{sg} + \rho_{ss}) - (\rho_{sw} + \rho_{ww}) \quad (9)$$

The ρ_{sg} is prominent due to salt-polar group (N^+H_3 and $-COO^-$) interactions than of salt $-CH_2-$, as the salts decrease electrostriction of water with decrease in ρ_{sw} and increase in ρ_{ss} . The ρ_{ww} remains same and explains an increase in ρ^0 with salt concentrations with higher ρ^0 values for I^- with larger composition effect on ion-ion

interactions than of Cl^- for small sized cations. With size of cations from Rb^+ to Cs^+ , the I^- does not remain so effective and Cl^- dominates over interactions and the difference in ρ^0 values is larger for Gly with stronger Gly-salt interactions, optionally ion-hydration may make an effective linkage with zwitterion-hydration producing larger volume for Cs^+ and Rb^+ . The ρ^0 values of aq CsCl are lower than RbCl-water but Gly in aq CsCl produces higher values by 0.0005 g cm^{-3} than of RbCl-water (Table 3). Thus Gly strengthens the Cs^+ -water interaction due to large size of Cs^+ but ρ^0 values of Gly for LiCl to KCl decrease with size and seem to depend on decrease in screening effect with size and concludes that I^- protects size effect of cations. Probably filled and unfilled d or p orbital stabilizes ion-water interactions. The S_d values of Gly for salts are noted as $LiCl > RbCl >$

NaCl > KCl > CsCl and LiI > NaI > KI > CsI > RbI. Here, the RbCl produces higher values than NaCl, KCl and CsCl but lower than LiCl, this depicts that Gly due to empty $4d$ orbital of Rb^+ strengthen Rb^+ -water interactions breaking water structure and strengthening Rb^+ -water and Rb^+ - $^-OOCCH_2-N^+H_2$ interactions. The factors cause higher packing influence on Gly for salts, also Na^+ , K^+ and Cs^+ form Na^+ - $^-OOCCH_2-N^+H_2$, K^+ - $^-OOCCH_2-N^+H_2$ and Cs^+ - $^-OOCCH_2-N^+H_2$ interactions. However with composition of Gly for salts an order of S_d is found as LiCl > RbCl > NaCl > KCl > CsCl and LiI > NaI > KI > CsI > RbI. It confirms contribution of polarization of I^- and integrates size with minor deviations for CsI and RbI due to screening remarkably shift behavior of halide salts of alkali metals and regulates Gly-Gly interactions.

Viscosity :

Contribution of size of Li^+ assessed from difference of ρ^0 values between chloride and iodide salts depict that I^- with Li^+ causes noticeable difference. It concludes that I^- polarization is more effective for stronger screening effect and weaker for Cs^+ , as a result the η values of aq. iodide salts are found lower than chlorides except NaI and NaCl pair. It proves that chloride salts on flow may not follow Newtonian motion so cause maximum torsional forces while due to polarized I^- the iodide salts may stick to laminar flow. Difference in ρ^0 and η values of iodide and chloride salts and of Gly for salts (Table 5) shows that $\Delta\rho$ values are higher and $\Delta\eta$ lower except for LiI-LiCl with Gly and weighs contribution of Gly on I^- polarization due to strengthening effect of Gly on ion-water interactions by breaking water structure. It favors structure breaking action for aq. salts and higher ρ^0 values for Gly for iodide salts due to stronger I^- - $N^+H_3CH_2COO^-$ interaction. It causes structuredness hence ρ^0 values of Gly-system are higher than of binary salts and η values for iodides are lower than of chlorides. The I^- -water and I^- - $N^+H_3CH_2COO^-$ interactions are stronger and hydration sphere of I^- is seen to be small sized with Newtonian flow. However slope values for η did not follow a particular pattern but for KI, RbI and CsI are noted to have higher η (Fig. 1) values than of chloride counterparts. Here a presence of d orbital seems to make difference perhaps due to screening pattern, in general, S_d values for Gly are noted higher for iodide salts except RbI, which has lower S_d than others in series. Unlike aq salts, the B values for Gly therein are almost of opposite trends infer Gly to weaken ion-water interactions of Li^+ and Na^+ with similar effect of Cl^- and I^- .

However from KCl to CsCl including RbI, are seen to strengthen but for KI and CsI weaken. Such trends of B values denote that NH_3^+ and COO^- groups disrupt bulk water strengthening water-Gly and salt-water-Gly interactions. Notably a decrease in B values by 5.973 of Gly for LiCl and NaCl proves weakening of interaction due to greater affinity for water repelling water molecules from hydrophilic polar ends or hydrophobic water of $-CH_2-$. An increase in values proves that cations get associated with hydrated water of polar groups instead of repelling water. Here Gly-water-cation interactions may not be denied with Gly effects on KCl-water interactions, as B values of aq KCl are lower than that Gly. And has remarkable influence on Rb^+ interactions with maximum B values among Gly-salt systems for both anions however larger values are for Cl^- by 0.0012. Thus B values of Gly for RbCl proves with stronger affinity for water and get incorporated in hydrated water repelling it to another phase with development of microphase of aqueous RbCl. It further decreases when Rb^+ is taken with I^- of RbI, as B values for its system are higher than CsI as it has negative B values for Gly and could be attributed to its mild effect on Gly-water interactions. However like ρ^0 there is regularity in order of B values of Gly in iodide salts (Table 4).

Excess viscosity, η^E and function (Y^E) :

In general, η^E values of chloride salts are lower than of iodides by ± 0.005 and seems to facilitate ion-water interactions slightly stronger than of chloride's via hydrogen bonding. The η^E values for LiCl after 0.15 to 0.3344 mol kg^{-1} , are negative and decrease with composition and for 1.0398 mol kg^{-1} NaCl also decrease. It confirms that interactions between ion-water decrease with concentration, notably Rb^+ gives negative and CsCl positive values. It indicates that Rb^+ -water interaction decrease with concentrations while CsCl increase, η^E for iodide salts is positive and supports Rb^+ -water interactions due to hydrogen bonding. The η^E values of Gly for salts are positive and prove that interactions between Gly-ion-water, Gly-Gly-ion, Gly-ion-ion and Gly-water-water are stronger. However η^E values for Gly are slightly lower by 0.002 than salts (Table 4) and Y^E function of salts is positive and indicates mutual loss of ion-water interactions while for Gly the values are positive and proves an enhancement of $N^+H_3CH_2COO^-$ -cations interactions (Fig. 2). The values for Cl^- are higher by 0.005 than I^- salts which cast weakening of ion-water are stronger than I^- . Fig. 3 clearly depicts the Y^E for salts and Gly-salt systems, Gly-salt systems including LiCl and CsI

have positive while others negative, it infers that Gly strengthen the ion-water interactions while others systems mildly weaken hydrogen bonding involved in ion-water interactions. It is proven that iodide salts behave as water structure breaker and RbCl mild maker, NaCl, KCl and CsCl slightly less structure breaker than iodides. The η^E values for KCl continuously increase (Fig. 2) with lower values for RbCl and CsCl, the iodide salts except CsI produce continuous increase. These trends infer the weaker ion-ion interaction for RbCl and CsCl, and an increase in values for Gly with salts proves that zwitterion does effect the ion-ion interactions. The Y^E values for salts (Fig. 3) are negative confirming greater reorientation in water structure by ions but positive values for Gly in salts illustrate that a shift from ionic to molecular interactions consumes less energy and bulk water reorientation due to hydrophobic interactions. It highlights a predominance of salt polar group over salt-non polar group interaction and a decrease in electrostriction with salts and concentration. However gradual decrease in molecular forces with salt concentration is responsible for the leveling effect. From Li^+ to Cs^+ as the shell no increase from $2s^1$ to $6s^1$ the attribute to the shielding/screening effect on nuclear charge distribution on the larger orbital of the cations. Such influence is noted to be strengthened by iodide anion and illustrate a higher concentration effect for iodide salt than chlorides (Fig. 3). The iodide with larger size and ionization potential monitor the ion-ion interaction with composition. It results could be viewed in a light of single ion contribution, as with each series of salts the chloride and iodide anion remains common. Thus larger influence of iodide or ion-ion interaction is noted of Na^+ but with the size of cation the S_v values were lowered. It substantiates that size of the cation weakens the structure breaking action of cations. The values of intensive functions ascertain that the cations of earth metal group IA in association of I^- do cause structure making. Thus comparatively the Rb^+ and Cs^+ with d -orbital are observed to strengthen the Gly-Gly and Gly-water interactions as to those of the Na^+ , K^+ and Li^+ ions. The LiCl with minimum S_v values direct almost least influence on Gly-water and Gly-Gly interactions while Gly with CsI has 0.114 value due to weaker interactions of Cs^+ and I^- with $-\text{COO}^-$ and $-\text{NH}_3^+$ groups. The value of Falkenhagen constant A have been found negative for KCl, KI, RbI and signify that these salts have weaker structure breaking tendency on water among both the series. The A values for LiCl are found negative and predict that as compared to the other salts it has stronger nuclear charge on its outer shell electron have to destabi-

lize the water as compared to other salts. Our results are supported by Feakins *et al.*³⁰, however dielectric constant caused by these salts do play key role to monitor the interactions and could be calculated by Rohdewald and Moldner³⁰⁻³². The values are almost of same order for chloride and iodide salts that prove the similar structure making effect of Gly on salt water interactions.

Experimental

Salts and glycine (A.R., Sigma and Merck) were used after drying at 110°C for 12 h and then vacuo over P_2O_5 at room temperature for minimum 24 h, dryness was checked with anhydrous CuSO_4 salt. Triple distilled water deionized by passing through two Cole-Parmer mixed bed ion exchange column and of conductivity less than $6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, was used for solutions w/w. The densities and viscosities were measured with $20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$ bicapillary pycnometer and Ubbelohde flow shear viscometer thermostated to better than $\pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$, read with Beckman thermometer. The temperature was maintained by electric relay encircuited with contact thermometer and 25 Watt immersion rod along with circulation of cold water by circulatory pump through copper coil dipped in water bath. The solutions in pycnometer and viscometer were thermostated for about 30 min for calibrations with water and sodium chloride solutions. The weighings were obtained with 0.01 mg Dhona balance, model 100DS and efflux time with $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}$ electronic racer.

Conclusion :

The negative B values for salts for binary system show that ion-ion interaction is stronger and spontaneous, except KCl, KI and RbI with weaker ion-ion interactions with their compositions. And no much significance is attached with the value of D although it may show composition effect on ion-ion interactions. The B coefficient is an adjustable parameter having positive or negative value and measure effective hydrodynamic volume of solvated ions/Gly-solvent interactions. Its values for salts are negative indicating that ion-solvent interaction are weaker and behave as structure breaker.

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